

A 1D-3D COUPLED APPROACH FOR AIR-COOLED TURBINE UNSTEADY FLOW SIMULATION

WANG Shiji
School of Aerospace
Engineering,
Tsinghua University
Beijing, China

XU Chunxiao
School of Aerospace
Engineering, Tsinghua
University
Beijing, China

LIU Zhao
School of Energy and
Power Engineering,
Xi'an Jiaotong University
Xi'an, China

ZHOU Jie
AECC Commercial
Aircraft Engine Co.,Ltd
Shanghai, China

ABSTRACT

The increasing demand for a higher efficiency air-cooled turbine component calls for improved predictions of turbine performances, especially on unsteady conditions. However, detailed modelling of airfoils with internal cooling structures would cause an unaffordable cost in actual engineering. This paper proposes a simulation method combining the source term method with one-dimensional flow network calculations to efficiently model the interaction between film cooling flows and mainstream hot gas flows in multi-row unsteady simulations. The proposed approach significantly reduces computational complexity by equivalently representing film cooling hole flows as momentum and energy source terms, while retaining the key physical characteristics of flow interaction effects.

The engineering applicability of the proposed method and tools in predicting internal flow characteristics was validated by comparing the blade internal flow test results with one-dimensional flow network calculations. Subsequently, a bidirectional 1D-3D coupled solution is achieved by employing user routines and functions to extract real-time flow field data as boundary conditions for 1D flow network calculation. Results are compared to the fully modeled case as baseline, and a lag-time modification was applied. The study demonstrates that the proposed method can effectively simulate the influences of cooling jet flows under unsteady conditions with a satisfactory computational accuracy.

KEYWORDS

Air-cooled turbine; URANS; 1D flow network model

NOMENCLATURE

Latin Symbols

A	Area
Eff	Isentropic efficiency
W	Mass flow rate
Q	Volumetric flow rate
V	Volume

l	Length
n	Number of time step
t	Time
v	Velocity

Subscripts

ave	average
c	cooling flow
cor	corrected
le	leading edge
h	hole
lag	lag
max	maximum
ps	pressure side
ss	suction side
stp	time step

1. INTRODUCTION

Gas turbines play a crucial role in power generation and aircraft propulsion systems. To optimize the performance and efficiency of gas turbines, effective cooling systems are required due to the extreme gas temperatures of turbines inlet during operation. In this case, numerical simulations of cooling flows have become essential for understanding and optimizing both thermal and aerodynamic performance of air-cooled turbines.

Over the past few decades, numerous numerical methods have been developed to simulate the cooling flow within gas turbines, which can generally be divided into two categories: full CFD simulation methods and source-term methods.

The full CFD simulation method refers to cases where cooling holes and slots are modeled with minimal or no simplification, using relatively detailed grids to model the geometrical features within the computational domain. The advantage of this approach lies in its ability to provide detailed flow-field information, and it is frequently employed in Direct Numerical Simulation (DNS) and Large-Eddy Simulation (LES) studies. However, direct simulation requires complex meshing,

a very large number of elements, and more computation resources, making it difficult to meet the rapid iterative requirements of practical engineering design. To improve design efficiency, Chen and Dong^[1] developed a structured meshing methodology for full-span film-cooled turbine blades based on ICFM CFD, enabling automated grid generation for film-cooling geometries. In 2011, B. Lad and L. He of Oxford University also proposed an immersed structural meshing approach^[2] to enhance solution accuracy, which significantly reduced mesh count while improving computational efficiency.

In contrast, the source-term method avoids additional mesh refinement by introducing mass, momentum, and energy source terms within the control volume of the cooling hole exit. This results in shorter computational time and easier implementation, making it a more widely adopted approach in engineering design practice. In 1998, Peter Dahlander^[3] first developed an injection model for coolant jets and tested it with various blowing ratios, showing good agreement between simulations and experimental data. Tartinville and Hirsch^[4] employed a uniform source-term model to simulate film cooling on flat plates and leading edges. When the mesh was refined, the source-term model allows an accurate prediction of the cooling effectiveness compared with full CFD simulations. Zeng Jun et al.^[5] applied the source-term method in a numerical study of a high-pressure turbine nozzle guide vane, modeling an entire row of film-cooling holes as a slot whose area was equivalent to the total hole area. Mass, momentum, energy, and turbulence source terms were defined at each slot surface element, and the results showed good agreement with experiments, confirmed the accuracy of the source-term approach for engineering design purposes. Kusterer et al.^[6] first proposed a cylindrical-hole model in which local mass, momentum, and energy sources are imposed within a finite cylindrical control volume positioned above the nominal hole exit. Similarly, Kampe and Völker^[7] developed a jet source-term method employing irregular control volumes based on CFD-derived correlations to define jet trajectories and cross-sectional shapes at different positions, which also shows great potential in cooling flow simulations.

Since multi-row cooling simulations using full CFD method already require significantly more mesh than the source-term approach, moreover, unsteady flow analysis further increases computational cost compared to steady-state simulations. Thus, performing unsteady simulations with full internal cooling structures becomes prohibitively expensive. Nevertheless, neglecting coolant boundary conditions can lead to misleading conclusions, Wang^[8] observed in stator-clocking optimizations and found that cooling flows have a non-negligible influence on results, designs optimized under un-cooled turbine, even if velocity triangles were maintained, could not be directly applied to the air-cooled turbines. P. Adami et al.^[9] employed multi-block unstructured meshing in trailing edge simulations and unsteady flow studies, reducing memory requirements while maintaining geometrical flexibility. Zhang et al.^[10] modeled film-cooling holes partially, retaining only the throat and downstream features, which also yielded good results. However, it should be emphasized that for blade-surface film holes

including those on the airfoil, trailing edge, and tip regions, when the internal flow passages are not interconnected, it becomes difficult to specify accurate pressure or mass-flow boundary conditions. Consequently, such simplifications cannot fully capture variations in coolant outflow induced by unsteady mainstream fluctuations.

To address this challenge, this study develops a program named TBCCS (Turbine Blade Coolant Coupling Simulation), which implies user-defined subroutines of ANSYS CFX to dynamically acquire real-time flow field data near the exit of the film-cooling holes. These data serve as input for one-dimensional flow-network calculation, through which the mass flow rate, temperature, and velocity at each coolant injection location are determined. Subsequently, these source terms are updated accordingly, enabling a tightly-coupled iterative process between the one-dimensional network model and the three-dimensional computational fluid dynamics simulation.

2. ONE-DIMENSIONAL NET FLOW

The 1D flow network method is a widely used simplified technique in the analysis of fluid flow inside engines^{[11]-[13]}, particularly for the calculation of flow distribution, and other relevant parameters in Secondary Air Systems (SAS) or air-cooled airfoils. This method assumes that the SAS flow is essentially one-dimensional, which allows for simplifications in modeling complex, three-dimensional flow phenomena.

2.1 Key Concepts

Internal cooling passages of the airfoils together with the coolant holes and slots connected to the mainstream can be regarded as a network composed of elements with different flow and heat transfer characteristics. By jointly solving the one-dimensional flow network formed by these elements, the temperature, pressure, mass flow rate, and velocity of each element can be obtained, thereby determining the coolant boundary conditions at the locations of the film-cooling holes and slots on the blade surface.

This method assumes that the flow properties (velocity, pressure, and density) are uniform across any cross-section perpendicular to the flow direction. In reality, flow inside turbines is three-dimensional, but the one-dimensional assumption simplifies the analysis and is useful when the detailed geometry and flow fields are complex.

The one-dimensional flow network calculation module treats the entire air system as a network composed of elements with different flow and heat transfer characteristics. The inlet and outlet of each element are referred to as nodes, and the serial number of the upstream element outlet node must match the inlet node of the downstream element. Elements connected in series form branches, while the intersection of branches is defined as a chamber, which is also part of the node system. In this way, the entire air network can be regarded as a combination of branches containing various elements. By specifying the serial number of node and chamber for the inlets and outlets of each element or branch, the program can automatically connect the elements in sequence to determine the airflow path. Elements are classified by type, including tubes, holes, pin fins, ribs, etc., each assigned

a specific code. The flow loss and heat transfer characteristics of each type of element have been experimentally validated and calibrated, and empirical correlations have been established.

During the calculation, initial values of pressure and temperature are assigned for each chamber. Computations are then carried out branch by branch to obtain the mass flow corresponding to chamber pressure and temperature. The chamber pressure is corrected according to the requirement of mass equilibrium, and the chamber temperature is corrected based on energy equilibrium. The process proceeds iteratively, and convergence is considered achieved when the chamber flows reach balance and the variations in chamber pressure and temperature between two successive iterations remain within the preset limits.

2.2 Test Object and Instrumentation

To verify the prediction accuracy of the one-dimensional flow network calculations, an internal flow test was used to check the flow distribution of different flow paths, the coolant flow rates of each airflow path under different pressure ratios are acquired and the pressure variations along the flow path are also obtained. The results were compared and analyzed with the flow network calculation results of TBCCS.

The object selected is rotor blades of high-pressure turbine. Cooling structure of the test blade is shown in Figure 1, which adopts a six-chamber structure with three airflow paths:

- First Path (Chamber I-II): Chamber I is an impact chamber using combined impact-film cooling method; Chamber II adopts a combined convection-film cooling method.
- Second Path (Chamber III-V): This is a three-fold forward turning channel using combined convection film cooling.
- Third Path (Chamber VI): Chamber VI supplies the cooling air of trailing edge, uses root inlet air with a baffle to control the flow rate.

FIGURE 1: INTERNAL COOLING GEOMETRY AND INSTRUMENTATIONS OF ROTOR

Static pressure holes are arranged along the surface of the blade in the direction of the cooling air flow. Diameter of the static pressure holes is 0.5mm, which is perpendicular to the internal chamber wall, the blades are fabricated through 3D-

printing. Additionally, there are 4 total pressure measurement points on the inlet flange. Measurement points are arranged on both the pressure and suction sides of the same channel, with the points on either side serving to cross-check each other. The test consists of 5 different blades, all with the same design configuration, but due to variations in fabrication and perforation processes, the actual measured results of the blades are not completely the same. To obtain generally representative test results, the measured values, including the actual hole diameter and physical flow rate of the cooling air, are taken as the average of all 5 blades.

2.3 Model Validation

The one-dimensional flow network model of the TBCCS was constructed based on theoretical geometric dimensions. The ambient pressure was applied as the outlet boundary conditions of the flow network calculation, and the measured pressure and temperature of the cooling supply plenum were adopted as the inlet boundary conditions. Film-hole diameters were corrected according to the inspection results of the test blades. During the calculation, pressure loss coefficients for selected elements were adjusted based on prior engineering experience.

As illustrated in the Fig.2~Fig.4, the coolant mass flow in each cavity increases with supply pressure ratio, and the deviation between TBCCS predictions and experimental measurements remains essentially constant across different pressure ratio conditions. This consistency demonstrates that the applied correction methodology exhibits strong adaptability to variations in blade cooling operating conditions.

FIGURE 2: FRONT CHANNEL COOLING FLOW VARIATION UNDER DIFFERENT SUPPLY PRESSURE

FIGURE 3: MIDDLE CHANNEL COOLING FLOW VARIATION UNDER DIFFERENT SUPPLY PRESSURE

FIGURE 4: REAR CHANNEL COOLING FLOW VARIATION UNDER DIFFERENT SUPPLY PRESSURE

To further analyze the variation of pressure loss along the flow path, Fig.5~7 presents the differences of static pressure obtained from both experimental measurements and TBCCS calculations. The abscissa represents the serial number by chart count, while the ordinate denotes the static pressure of each nodes.

It can be observed that although certain loss elements exhibit some deviations in flow-loss coefficients compared with the experimental results, the overall agreement is satisfactory. By adjusting the pressure loss coefficients of certain elements, the pressure along the internal cooling passages can be captured with reasonable accuracy.

FIGURE 5: STATIC PRESSURE COMPARISON ALONG FRONT CHANNEL

FIGURE 6: STATIC PRESSURE COMPARISON ALONG MID CHANNEL

FIGURE 7: STATIC PRESSURE COMPARISON ALONG REAR CHANNEL

3. COUPLING SIMULATION

3.1 Approach

In CFD simulations, a user-defined subroutine in ANSYS CFX was employed to enable real-time coupling with the one-dimensional network solver during the computation, thus achieving an internal flow network solution that is based on the instantaneous flow field. This approach avoids the mismatch of interface parameters that would arise if the aerodynamic field of the turbine and the internal coolant flow calculations were performed independently.

When ANSYS CFX starts the solution process, TBCCS is first invoked via the User Junction Box Routines to initialize the coolant source terms according to the input file. It should be noted that the closer the initial coolant boundary conditions are to the final converged state, the faster the convergence of the program will be. On the contrary, unreasonable initial conditions (e.g., an excessively high coolant flow rate leading to supersonic coolant velocity) may cause execution errors and compromise the coupled solution process. The whole process is illustrated in Figure 8.

After ANSYS CFX Solver completes case initialization, the formal solution process begins, which involves two levels of iterative loops: the coefficient loop (pseudo time-step of inner iterations) and the time-step loop (physical time advancement). During the coefficient loop, the physical time step remains fixed. At the end of each inner iteration, TBCCS outputs the instantaneous flow-field data into a temporary file. A predefined criterion is then checked to determine whether the coolant boundary conditions need to be updated. If yes, TBCCS is called to use the current flow-field data as outlet boundary conditions for the one-dimensional internal flow network calculation, result files are stored. Subsequently, the TBCCS subroutines update the coolant boundary conditions and other related computational settings in ANSYS CFX through User CEL Functions. The solution then proceeds with the next 3D-CFD iteration of the hot-gas/coolant flow field until the convergence criterion is reached.

In steady-state simulations, the flow field is assumed to be time-invariant, and therefore the solution relies solely on pseudo time-step iterations. An initial threshold number of iterations is set to constant during the early stages of the simulation,

preventing from affecting the convergence of the internal flow network. Once this threshold is reached, the TBCCS is invoked periodically (at a fixed iteration interval determined based on case size and expected convergence) to update the coolant boundary conditions through the flow-network calculation and user-defined function output modules.

FIGURE 8: FLOWCHART OF 1D-3D COUPLED CALCULATION

In unsteady multi-row simulations, transient flow fields are computed at each step. For every physical time step, a fixed number of inner iterations is prescribed, and the number of coefficient loop iterations cannot be adaptively increased based on convergence. In this case, the initial threshold for the coefficient loop must be smaller than the total number of prescribed iterations, with sufficient remaining iterations reserved after the coolant boundary condition update. Moreover, since unsteady cases require more convergence steps than steady

ones, the initial threshold for physical time steps should also be higher. Moreover, the flow field changes from one physical time step to another, so coolant boundary conditions must be updated at every time step without any iteration interval.

3.2 Numerical Validation

To verify the feasibility of the coupled 1D–3D flow solver, a coupled flow analysis was carried out on a single-stage vanes and blades of a certain aero-engine. Two approaches were employed for comparison. The first is a full 3D refined simulation that explicitly models the internal cooling passages and film-cooling holes, thereby resolving both internal and external flow regions of the blade, as shown in Fig 9. The second approach is a coupled computation in which only the external flow domain of the blade is modeled, while the film-hole outlet flow parameters are calculated with TBCCS.

FIGURE 9: MESH OF VANES AND BLADES

To reduce computational resource requirements, the guide vane model retained only the trailing edge cooling slots due to its significant influence on downstream flow field non-uniformity. For the rotor blade, one row of film-cooling holes was preserved each on the location of leading edge, pressure side, and suction side. These holes are representative enough of common design practice and are of significant relevance for film-cooling performance assessment.

Table 1 presents the performance of turbine calculated by two different approaches. It can be seen from the table that the discrepancy between the two approaches is significantly smaller than the engineering acceptable level.

TABLE 1: NUMERICAL RESULTS OF THE TWO APPROACHES

Parameter	Unit	Base	TBCCS	Devi.
Isentropic Efficiency	-	0.8916	0.8911	0.06%
Total Pressure Ratio	-	2.8513	2.8522	0.03%
Corrected Mass Flow	kg/s	3.0062	3.0053	0.03%
Coolant for Rotor1	g/s	130.67	129.88	0.67%

Fig.10~Fig.11 present the variation of turbine corrected mass flow and total coolant flow of the rotor blade over time step. Although the two sets of results exhibit good agreement, a certain degree of asynchrony was observed.

FIGURE 10: CORRECTED MASS FLOW VERSUS TIME STEP

FIGURE 11: TOTAL COOLANT MASS OF ROTOR VERSUS TIME STEP

A further analysis of the instantaneous fluctuations of coolant mass through each film-cooling hole at midspan are presented in Fig. 12~Fig.14. It can be observed that, at different hole locations, the source-term approach is generally able to capture the variation in coolant flow rate induced by the unsteady fluctuations of the hole exit boundary conditions. However, the peaks of the coolant mass variations of TBCCS appear slightly advanced compared to the full 3D refined simulation case. This phenomenon is likely due to the time delay between the pressure fluctuation at the film-hole exit and the actual discharge of coolant through the hole. In high-speed rotating blades, time of this phase lag is not negligible relative to the physical time step, and thus manifests as a “lag effect” in coolant injection.

FIGURE 12: MASS OF MIDSPAN HOLE ON LEADING EDGE VERSUS TIME STEP

FIGURE 13: MASS OF MIDSPAN HOLE ON SUCTION SIDE VERSUS TIME STEP

FIGURE 14: MASS OF MIDSPAN HOLE ON PRESSURE SIDE VERSUS TIME STEP

In TBCCS, one-dimensional network solver assumes that the pressure difference between the interior and exterior of each film hole reaches equilibrium within each time step. As a result, when a pressure fluctuation occurs, the coolant mass flow predicted for that time step is immediately injected into the domain as a source term. This leads to a lack of synchronization with the base case regarding the phase of coolant mass flow variations.

3.3 Modification for Time-Lag

To correct for this lag effect, a time-step adjustment method needs to be established. If the cross-sectional area of the film-cooling hole is denoted as A , the volumetric flow rate Q_c through the hole inlet can be expressed as Eq. (1).

$$Q_c(t) = A \cdot v(t) \quad (1)$$

where $v(t)$ is the instantaneous velocity. Volume of the film-cooling hole channel V_c can be expressed as the product of area A and the channel length l_h as Eq. (2). For holes of non-standard geometry, an equivalent length can be obtained by dividing the channel volume by its cross-sectional area.

$$V_c = A \cdot l_h \quad (2)$$

When the integral volumetric flow rate Q_c equals to the channel volume V_c , the coolant completely fills the passage and begins to overflow. The time elapsed during this process corresponds to the lag time t_{lag} for the coolant mass flow response to pressure fluctuations, given in Eq. (3).

$$l_{hole} = \int_t^{t+t_{lag}} v(t) dt \quad (3)$$

Since the lag time is generally small enough, the velocity variation can be approximated as linear. The above integral can therefore be discretized as Eq. (4).

$$l_{hole} = \frac{t_{lag} \cdot [v(t + t_{lag}) + v(t)]}{2} \quad (4)$$

To simplify the calculation, the average coolant velocity v_{ave} obtained from steady-state results is used together with l_{hole} to define an average lag time $t_{lag,ave}$. Substituting this into the previous expression yields Eq. (5).

$$t_{lag} = \frac{2 \cdot l_h}{v(t + t_{lag,ave}) + v(t)} \quad (5)$$

Defining t_{stp} as the physical time-step size in the unsteady calculation, the lag time can be converted into a discrete number of time steps n_{lag} as the rounding of t_{lag}/t_{stp} .

Before executing TBCCS, each film hole is assigned an initial lag time step $t_{lag,ave}$ based on steady-state results. A maximum lag time-step limit $n_{lag,max}$ is also prescribed to avoid excessive data storage in cases that the coolant flow rate and velocity are too small. During the simulation, if the current time step is smaller than the sum of the threshold time step and $n_{lag,max}$, no correction is applied, and the coolant boundary condition is directly assigned from the current solution. Once the current time step exceeds this limit, the algorithm evaluates the updated lag time t'_{lag} . This is compared against the current lag correction time t_{lag} (initialized as $t_{lag,ave}$, and updated iteratively in subsequent steps). If the difference between t'_{lag} and t_{lag} is larger than one physical time step and at the same time does not exceed $n_{lag,max}$, then t_{lag} is updated and set to t'_{lag} . Otherwise, if the lag time-step exceeds the limit, n_{lag} will be set to the maximum allowable value, as expressed below:

$$n_{lag} = \begin{cases} \text{round}\left(\frac{t_{lag}}{t_{stp}}, 0\right), & \text{abs}\left(\frac{t'_{lag} - t_{lag}}{t_{stp}}\right) < 1 \\ \text{round}\left(\frac{t'_{lag}}{t_{stp}}, 0\right), & 1 \leq \text{abs}\left(\frac{t'_{lag} - t_{lag}}{t_{stp}}\right) < n_{lag,max} \\ n_{lag,max}, & \frac{t'_{lag}}{t_{stp}} \geq n_{lag,max} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Fig.15~Fig.17 present the variation of film-hole coolant mass flow versus modified time step after applying time-lag correction. It can be seen that, following the correction, the peaks and valleys of coolant flow in the two cases exhibit good synchronization.

FIGURE 15: MASS OF MIDSPAN HOLE ON LEADING EDGE VERSUS MODIFIED TIME STEP

FIGURE 16: MASS OF MIDSPAN HOLE ON SUCTION SIDE VERSUS MODIFIED TIME STEP

FIGURE 17: MASS OF MIDSPAN HOLE ON PRESSURE SIDE VERSUS MODIFIED TIME STEP

Fig.18 presents the fluctuations of turbine isentropic efficiency over time step calculated by the TBCCS after applied time-lag modification. Compared to the full 3D refined baseline simulation case, a good agreement on peak and valley could be observed and an excellent time step synchronization was reached, further verifies the engineering applicability of this method.

FIGURE 18: ISENTROPIC EFFICIENCY VERSUS TIME STEP

4. CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that, with appropriate correction for the time-lag effect, the proposed 1D–3D coupling method can accurately capture the bidirectional influence between mainstream and cooling jet flows under unsteady conditions, while maintaining accuracy at engineering acceptable level. The method proves particularly suitable for unsteady performance

analysis of air-cooled turbine components and for assessing backflow margins in cooling holes subject to unsteady boundary conditions. Moreover, the approach provides an efficient and robust tool for turbine cooling design, with promising potential for extension to the optimization of airfoils and cooling configurations. Overall, the methodology establishes a low-cost yet high-fidelity simulation framework for the studies in air-cooled aeroengines and gas turbines.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was funded by National Major Project for Fundamental Research of China (J2019-II-0008-0028). The authors would also like to acknowledge the technical support of Zhang Jing and Huang Qihe in one-dimensional flow network establishment and calculations.

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